

Economic Development in Ahmednagar District, Maharashtra State, India

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Abstract: This research paper based on sources of secondary information, mainly using the 2011 census data as well as District Statistical Handbook at 2019. To study of economic inequality in Ahmednagar district, 15 factors have been used, while population factors and agricultural factors have also been considered. Also the Z score method is used to level these entire economic factors.

Key word: Economic Development, Regional Disparities, Agricultural, Ahmednagar District.

Introduction:

There are some factors of economic development which mainly include the total population engaged in primary second tertiary activity. In short, how many people are involved in economic development is important, and on top of that, today's production in that area depends. What are the factors for measuring regional disparity mainly include physical resource cultural factors and institute and technical factors. Regional disparities in the level of development are the product of regional disparities in the distribution of physical resources [3,4,5]. (Chandna R.C 2012)Regional disparities in cultural moorings as well as regional disparities in technology attainments and disparities in the institutional framework.

Study Area:

The present study Ahmednagar district has been selected as a study area. It extends between 18° 20' and 19° 59' north latitudes and 73° 40' to 75° 43' east longitudes (Map.1). The total length of Ahmednagar district is 200 kilometers and Width it is 210 kilometers. This Ahmednagar district naturally physical into three divisions. The first is the Sahyadri mountain range. There are various mountain ranges like Kalsubai, Adula, Baleshwar and Harishchandragad in this range, second Plateau third plains area. The major rivers in the district are Godavari and Bhima and tributaries Pravara, Mula, Sina, Dhora, Kukdi.

Aims and Objective:

The main objective of this research is to study the economic inequality in Ahmednagar district. There are 15 main factors considered to study economic inequality. It is important to study the effect of these factors on economic inequality. The objectives of this research are also to study economic inequality with the help of Z score.

Research Methodology:

The secondary data source of information has been used for this research. The information has been collected from Ahmednagar District Statistical Handbook for the year 2019 in front of the district. Fifteen factors have been used to study economic

Regional disparities in the level of development are not the product of the regional disparities in the distribution of natural resources alone but are the function of combined effect of regional disparities in the distribution of natural resources, cultural background, technological attainments and intuitional framework associated with the political background. In order to overcome the socio-political and economic disparities of a region, it is necessary to formulate goal strategies based on the geographical background of the region. Accordingly, it is necessary to implement a plan in this area. Human Resources and Natural Resources are the two factors that contribute to reducing the social and economic inequality of any region [10, 15, 16].

inequality and to score the level of economic development from these fifteen factors, the Z score is the statistical method used. The four levels of this economic level are as follows, Level of Development, Very Low Development, Low Development, Moderate Development, and Development. As well as the Z score index value

level is created in that format as shown in Table 1. The Economic Indicators are Percentage of Net sown area (X1), Number of shallow tube-wells (X2), Number of deep tube-wells (X3), Number of commercial banks (X4), Number of gramin banks (X5), Number of cooperative societies (X6), Number of Fertilizer

Very Low Development:

The very low development level is based on the level of Z score, it is between levels -1.0 to -0.4, so it includes two talukas. In Ahmednagar district, in very low development, there are two talukas, mainly Jamkhed and Shrirampur talukas. This development depends on these fifteen factors which means that these fifteen factors have not been developed in these talukas or you can see their deficiency.

Low Development:

Considering the above fifteen factors, you come across five talukas in low development, mainly Akole Parner, Nevase Sangamner and Shrigonda talukas. This means that the above fifteen factors are underdeveloped, so you see a lot of regional disparities. In short, you don't see economic development in these talukas. Out of these talukas, Parner, Nevasa and Shrigonda talukas are in drought prone areas.

Moderate Development:

Fifteen factors are important factors in the inequality of economic development in Ahmednagar district. Through these factors and the Z score method, seven tehsils come into moderate development. Those tehsils are karjat, Nagar, Pathardi, Rahata, Rahuri, Shovgaon,

Depot (X7), Percentage of Agricultural labour (X8), Percentage of Cultivators (X9), Road Length (X10) Percentage of HH, (X11) Percentage of Other workers, (X12) Percentage of Marginal workers, (X13), (X14) Irrigated Area, (X15) Literacy rate in Percentage

MAP NO 02: ECONOMIC DEVELOPMENT

Kopargoan. According to the method of Z score, the value of development is 0 to 1.1. Although literacy rate is low in Shevgaon and Pathardi talukas, the rest of the area is moderately developed as per Z score and agriculture is not developed here as there are irrigation problems or limitations.

Table No 01: Level of Economic Development

Level Z Score	Level of Development	Name of the Tehsils	Number of the Tehsil
-1.0 to -0.4	Very Low Development	Jamkhed, Shrirampur	02
-0.3 to 0.0	Low Development	Akole, Parner, Newasa, Sangamner, Shrigonda,	05
0. to 1.1	Moderate Development	karjat,, Nagar, Pathardi, Rahata, ,Rahuri, ,Shovgaon, Kopargoan.	07
More Than 1.2	Development	-	00

Conclusion:

The help of this Z score, you can find four levels in economic development, very low development, low, moderate and development. It is clear from this that there are two talukas in Very Low, there are five talukas in Low, there are seven talukas in Moderate and there is no taluka in development.

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